

SURVEY ON ETHNOMEDICINAL USES OF SIDDHALEPA BALM AMONG SRI LANKANS

¹*Edirimuni Rodrigo Hathishiya Sujatha Silva Ediriweera, ²Priyani Asoka Paranagama, ³Angulugaha Gamage Aruni Champika, ⁴Lankani Hettigoda

¹Ph.D. (Peradeniya), M.D.(Ayu) Kayachikithsa Specialisation in Panchakarma(Varanasi), Dip in Yoga (Varanasi), D.A.M.S. (Hons) (Colombo) Emeritus Professor, Faculty of Indigenous Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka Consultant and Medical Superintendent, Siddhalepa Ayurveda Hospital Pvt. Ltd., Mount lavinia, Sri Lanka.

²Ph.D. in Chemistry (Glasgow,UK), M.Phil. In Chemistry (Kelaniya), B.Sc (Hons) in Chemistry (Kelaniya) Senior Professor, Dean, Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka Chair and Senior Professor, Department of Chemistry, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka Former Director, Institute of Indigenous Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka Treasurer (2023/2024), Chairperson of the Women Chemists Committee, Past President (2019/2020), Institute of Chemistry, Ceylon.

³D.A.M.S (Kelaniya) Directress / Assistanat Medical Superintendent Siddhalepa Ayurveda Hospital Pvt. Ltd., Mount lavinia, Sri Lanka.

⁴BSc (Hons) Chemistry, University College, University of London, MSc in Chemical Research, University College, University of London, Directress, Hettigoda Industries Pvt Ltd, Rathmalana, Sri Lanka.

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*Corresponding Author

Edirimuni Rodrigo Hathishiya Sujatha Silva Ediriweera

Ph.D. (Peradeniya), M.D.(Ayu) Kayachikithsa Specialisation in Panchakarma(Varanasi), Dip in Yoga (Varanasi), D.A.M.S. (Hons) (Colombo) Emeritus Professor, Faculty of Indigenous Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka Consultant and Medical Superintendent, Siddhalepa Ayurveda Hospital Pvt. Ltd., Mount lavinia, Sri Lanka.

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ABSTRACT

Siddhalepa balm is a herbal preparation developed by the traditional Ayurveda physician family, the Hettigoda family from Imaduwa, Sri Lanka. It is widely used in Sri Lanka as a home remedy for various ailments. Although it has been popular for decades, no scientific survey had been conducted to assess its usage among Sri Lankans. A multi-centre survey was carried out to study the usage of Siddhalepa balm among Sri Lankans. A total of 375 citizens participated in the study. Based on the results, it was found that the participant applied the balm to relieve headaches, muscular aches and pains, toothaches and swelling, various forms of arthritis such as rheumatic arthritis, osteoarthritis and gouty arthritis, common cold, sneezing, breathing difficulties or wheezing, fever, and insect bites. Eighty to ninety eight percent of participants reported experiencing instant relief or relief within an hour of application, except in cases of myalgia, where the figure was 61%. Relief lasted two hours or longer in 64% to 91% of participants, except in myalgia (46%). No adverse effects

were reported during the study. Therefore, it is concluded that Siddhalepa balm is a safe herbal product that provides rapid relief for a wide range of common ailments.

KEYWORDS: Siddhalepa balm, Headache, Myalgia, Rhino-sinusitis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Siddhalepa balm is a traditional herbal preparation developed by the Hettigoda family, a renowned lineage of traditional physicians. Siddhalepa balm has been a trusted over-the-counter (OTC) herbal remedy in Sri Lanka since 1934 for numerous ailments. Sri Lankans apply this balm externally to overcome headaches, colds, nasal congestion, muscle ache, joint pains and insect bites. Ingredients of Siddhalepa balm are eucalyptus oil (oil of *Eucalyptus globulus*, Family: Myrtaceae), citronella oil (oil of *Cymbopogon nardus*, Family: Poaceae), cinnamon oil (oil of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, Family: Lauraceae), camphor (waxy substance found in the wood of the *Cinnamomum camphora*, Family: Lauraceae), menthol (crystals of *Mentha piperita*, Family: Lamiaceae) and Pinus species twig-leaf oil (essential oil obtained from the twigs and the leaves of different species of pine including *Syncarpia glomulifera*, Family: Myrtaceae). These ingredients possess the properties of analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and decongestant properties. No known survey has been conducted to collect the usage of Siddhalepa balm among the Sri Lankan population. Therefore, the present study aims to collect the current applications of Siddhalepa balm in modern Sri Lankan society for various health conditions.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The survey was conducted as a multi-centre study at the Siddhalepa Ayurveda Hospital, Siddhalepa Center at Sripada, Siddhalepa Clinics at Horton Place, Pelawatta, and Negombo. In addition, survey data were collected through door-to-door visits covering diverse regions across Sri Lanka to ensure comprehensive and representative participation. A specially prepared questionnaire was used to collect data and the study was conducted from May 2025 to July 2025. A total of 375 participants from diverse age groups, geographic regions, and educational backgrounds were recruited. Each participant was instructed to complete the questionnaire independently. Written and verbal consent was obtained from participants before collection of data.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Age-wise distribution of siddhalepa balm usage by age group

According to the present study, the majority (41%) of participants who use Siddhalepa balm are aged over 50 years. Among the remaining users, 24% are between 41 and 50 years, 22% are between 31 and 40 years, and 12% are between 21 and 30 years. Usage is very low (1%) among participants aged between 15 and 20 years.

3.2. Gender-wise prevalence of Siddhalepa balm usage

According to the current study, 63% of females and 37% of males use Siddhalepa balm.

3.3. Prevalence of Siddhalepa balm usage

A high prevalence of Siddhalepa balm usage was observed among the participants, with 99% reporting its use. Only 1% of participants reported that they do not use Siddhalepa balm.

3.4. Duration-Based Incidence of Siddhalepa balm Usage

According to recent survey, 17% of participants have been using Siddhalepa balm for more than 50 years, 27% for 26 to 50 years, 31% for 16 to 25 years, 12% for 11 to 15 years, 8% for 6 to 10 years, 3% for 2 to 5 years, and 2% for up to two years.

3.5. Incidence of method of participants became aware of Siddhalepa balm

The majority of participants (66%) became aware of Siddhalepa balm through relatives, followed by 23% through advertisements, 8% through promotions, and 3% through other methods such as friends and in store displays.

3.6. Incidence of disease conditions that participants use Siddhalepa balm

Based on this study, participants use Siddhalepa balm to relieve various ailments, including headache (25%), common cold (20%), muscular aches and pains (16%), toothache and swelling (14%), arthritis namely rheumatic arthritis, osteoarthritis and gouty arthritis (6%), sneezing (5%), insect bites (5%), difficulty in breathing or wheezing (4%), fever (4%) and other such as herbal steam therapy (1%).

3.7. Incidence of size of Siddhalepa balm bottles purchase by participants

According to present study participants prefer to purchase Siddhalepa balm bottles weighing 25g and 10g and their percentage is 30% and 28% respectively. Additionally, bottles weighing 50g (15%), 15g (11%), 100g (7%), 5g (6%), and 2.5g (3%) are also purchased by participants.

3.8. Frequency of Siddhalepa balm usage among Participants

The majority of participants (92%) reported using Siddhalepa balm when needed, while 4% use it daily and another 4% use it as a habitual practice.

3.9. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from headache, and the duration of the relief.

Sixteen percent of participants reported experiencing instant relief from headaches after applying Siddhalepa balm. Eighty-one percent experienced relief within one hour of application, 2% reported relief after more than an hour, and 1% experienced relief after a few days. Notably, none of the participants reported a lack of relief.

The duration of headache relief following application lasted more than two hours in 21% of participants, approximately two hours in 70%, around one hour in 6%, and only a few minutes in 3%.

3.10. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from common cold and the duration of the relief.

Fifteen percent of participants reported experiencing instant relief from common cold after applying Siddhalepa balm. Eighty-two percent of participants reported experiencing relief within less than one hour of application, 2% after more than one hour, and 1% after a few days. None of the participants reported a lack of relief.

Relief from common cold lasted more than two hours in 18% of participants, around two hours in 74%, around one hour in 7% and only a few minutes in 1% of participants.

3.11. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from sneezing and the duration of the relief

A total of 46% of participants experienced instant relief from sneezing upon applying Siddhalepa balm. Forty four percent of participants reported experiencing relief within less than one hour of application, 8% after more than one hour, and 2% after a few days. None of the participants reported a lack of relief.

Relief from sneezing lasted more than two hours in 51% of participants, around two hours in 26%, around one hour in 13% and only a few minutes in 10% of participants.

3.12. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from difficulty in breathing / wheezing and the duration of the relief

It was found that 38% of participants experienced immediate relief from difficulty in breathing or wheezing after applying Siddhalepa balm. An additional 57% reported relief within one hour of application. A further 2.5% experienced relief after more than one hour, while some (2.5%) participants noted improvement only after a few days.

Forty-five percent of participants reported that relief from difficulty in breathing or wheezing lasted more than two hours after applying Siddhalepa balm. Meanwhile, 19% experienced relief for approximately two hours, 29% for about one hour, and 7% reported that the relief lasted only a few minutes.

3.13. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from fever and the duration of the relief

Instant relief from fever after applying Siddhalepa balm was reported by 18% of participants. Relief within less than one hour was experienced by 66%, while 11% reported relief after more than one hour, and 5% after a few days. None of the participants reported no relief.

Relief from fever lasted more than two hours in 55% of participants, approximately two hours in 24%, around one hour in 15%, and only a few minutes in 6%.

3.14. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from Rheumatic arthritis / Osteoarthritis / Gouty arthritis and the duration of the relief

Instant relief from rheumatic arthritis, osteoarthritis, gouty arthritis after applying Siddhalepa balm was reported by 28% of participants, while 60% experienced relief within one hour. Ten percent of participants experienced relief one hour after applying the balm, while two percent reported relief after a few days. None of the participants reported a lack of relief.

The duration of relief varied: 38% of participants experienced relief lasting more than two hours, 28% reported relief lasting approximately two hours, 13% felt relief for around one hour, and 21% experienced relief for only a few minutes.

3.15. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from Toothache and Swelling and the duration of the relief

Twelve percent of participants reported instant relief from toothache, 86% experienced relief in less than one hour, 1% after more than one hour, and 1% within a few days.

The relief obtained from toothache remained more than two hours in 10 % of participants, around two hours in 80 %, approximately one hour in 6 % and only a few minutes in 4%. of participants.

3.16. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from Muscular aches and pains and the duration of the relief

Instant relief from muscular aches and pains after applying Siddhalepa balm was reported by 25% of participants. Additionally, 36% experienced relief within less than one hour, 38% experienced relief within more than one hour and 1% within a few days.

Relief from muscular aches and pain lasted more than two hours in 28% of participants, around two hours in 18%, approximately one hour in 50%, and only a few minutes in 4%.

3.17. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from insect bites and the duration of the relief

Thirty-five percent of participants reported experiencing instant relief from insect bites after applying Siddhalepa balm. Additionally, 53% experienced relief within less than an hour, 7% within more than an hour, and 5% after a few days.

According to 63% of participants, relief from pain due to insect bites lasted more than two hours. For 17% of participants, relief lasted around two hours, while 15% reported relief lasting about one hour. Only 5% experienced relief for few minutes.

3.18. Incidence and time taken to experience relief after applying Siddhalepa balm among participants suffering from other conditions and the duration of the relief

Present study reveals that participants apply Siddhalepa balm for other conditions such as herbal steam therapy. Participants reported that relief was experienced instantly (33%), within one hour (47%), after more than one hour (13%), and after a few days (7%).

Relief lasted more than two hours in 67% participants, around one hours in 16.5% and few minutes in 16.5% participants.

4. DISCUSSION

According to the present study, participants apply Siddhalepa balm externally to relieve headaches, muscular aches and pains, toothaches and swelling, various forms of arthritis namely rheumatic arthritis, osteoarthritis, and gouty arthritis, common cold, sneezing, breathing difficulties or wheezing, fever, and insect bites.

Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects of *Eucalyptus globulus*,^[1] *Cymbopogon nardus*,^[2] *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*,^[3,4] *Mentha piperita*.^[5] and *Cinnamomum camphora*.^[6,7] are scientifically proven. Therefore, Siddhalepa balm helps to subside headache, muscular aches and pains, toothache and various types of arthritis including rheumatic arthritis, osteoarthritis, and gouty arthritis.

Antipyretic effect of oil of *Eucalyptus globulus*,^[8] *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*^[9] and *Cinnamomum camphora*.^[10] are scientifically proven. Therefore, Siddhalepa balm helps to subside fever.

Antibacterial effect of oil of *Eucalyptus globulus*,^[11] *Cymbopogon nardus*^[12] *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*,^[13] *Mentha piperita*,^[14] *Syncarpia glomulifera*.^[15] and *Cinnamomum camphora*^[16] are scientifically proven. Hence, Siddhalepa balm is effective in management of toothache, common cold, sneezing, difficulty in breathing or wheezing and fever.

Antiallergic effect of *Eucalyptus globulus*,^[17] and *Cinnamomum camphora*.^[18] Therefore, Siddhalepa balm can counteract allergies due to insect bites and also allergies which produce difficulty in breathing or wheezing.

Cinnamaldehyde, 1,8-cineole, and eugenol are among the phytochemicals found in *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*.^[19] Cinnamaldehyde has demonstrated the highest anti-nociceptive effect in both acute and chronic phases.^[20] The essential oil from the leaves of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* is rich in eugenol.^[21] The anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic properties of eugenol have been scientifically demonstrated in animal models.^[22-23] *Cymbopogon nardus* is rich in phytochemicals such as citronellal, citronellol, and geraniol.^[24] The analgesic effect of citronellal has been confirmed through research,^[25] and it has also been shown to possess anti-inflammatory properties.^[26] Geraniol has been reported to exhibit anti-arthritic effects based on experimental findings.^[27] *Mentha piperita* contains a variety of phytochemicals, with menthol being one of the most prominent.^[28] Studies have shown that menthol produces analgesic effects by blocking sodium channels and inhibiting calcium influx.^[29] Additionally, menthol has demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties.^[30] *Eucalyptus globulus* is a rich

source of 1,8-cineole.^[31] The analgesic effect of 1,8-cineole is documented^[32] and its anti-inflammatory properties have been scientifically validated.^[33] Furthermore, 1,8-cineole has been reported as an effective anti-arthritic agent.^[34] *Syncarpia glomulifera* contains compounds such as tetragocarbene C and sideroxylin.^[35] Research findings suggest that these compounds, particularly tetragocarbene C and sideroxylin, are promising anti-inflammatory agents.^[35] Due to the properties of the phytochemicals present in the ingredients of Siddhalepa balm, it may help to alleviate headaches, muscular aches and pains, toothaches, and various forms of arthritis, including rheumatic, osteoarthritis, and gouty arthritis.

Rokonuzzman *et al.*^[26] reported that the phytochemical citronellal, found in *Cymbopogon nardus*, exhibits both antibacterial and antifungal properties. Additionally, geraniol has demonstrated antibacterial activity against staphylococci, particularly the *Staphylococcus epidermidis* strain.^[36] The antibacterial properties of menthol, derived from *Mentha piperita*, have been scientifically validated.^[37] The antibacterial effect of 1,8-cineole from *Eucalyptus globulus* has also been scientifically proven.^[38-39] Therefore, Siddhalepa balm is effective in managing toothache, common cold, sneezing, breathing difficulties such as wheezing, and fever.

Badger-Emeka *et al.*^[40] reported that cinnamaldehyde significantly suppressed the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-6, as well as nitric oxide (NO), in stimulated mast cells. These findings further support the potential of cinnamaldehyde (CA) to attenuate mast cell activation by inhibiting histidine decarboxylase (HDC) and modulating allergic responses^[41] stated that menthol, derived from *Mentha piperita*, provides symptomatic relief from nasal congestion associated with rhinitis and the sensation of dyspnea located with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), through its specific interaction with the CMR1 receptor on trigeminal nerve endings in the nose and upper airways. Therefore, Siddhalepa balm can counteract nasal congestion and difficulty in breathing or wheezing.

5. CONCLUSION

The traditional applications of Siddhalepa balm among Sri Lankans are supported by scientific evidence highlighting its bioactive properties and phytochemical properties. As a polyherbal formulation, Siddhalepa balm is reputed for its diverse therapeutic properties and long-standing role in traditional medicine.

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